

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF TEACHING HANDBALL SPORTS TO SENIOR STUDENTS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS**F.X.Karimov****Tashkent Financial Institute,****Department of Physical Culture and Sports, Acting Associate Professor****Karimov Bakhriddin Khurramovich****Termiz State Pedagogical Institute, theory and methodology of physical education and sports training, group 23-09 master's student and teacher of physical education at specialized school No. 1, Denov district, Surkhandarya region**

Annotation: the article talks about the features of teaching the type of handball sort to upper-graders, the role of the handball sport in educating the spiritual and volitional characteristics of schoolchildren, developing their physical qualities

Keywords: hand ball, strength, dexterity, agility, endurance, moral, willpower qualities, physical qualities.

Sports games have taken place in very ancient times from the way of life of young people as a means of upbringing, recreation and entertainment. Actions that make up games help develop moral and willful qualities: strength, dexterity, agility, endurance. At the same time, with the help of games, knowledge and skills that are important for survival are improved.

Sports games, which are used in the physical education classes of secondary schools, are very colorful. Sports games are an advanced high stage of action games. They differ in the accuracy of the composition of the participants from the action game, the size and marks of the field, the continuation of the game, the equipment and equipment, the variety of rules of the game, Steam allows you to conduct competitions of different categories. Competitions in sports games require great physical strength and willpower from the participants. Therefore, theoretical and practical aspects of sports games are taught in educational institutions.

Each sports game has its own unique feature. At the same time in sports games in particular gandbolda there are some similar signs that give them the opportunity to be divided into certain groups: as a team and individually, without approaching and approaching directly with his opponent. When determining the impact and importance of the handball game on the student's organism, it is necessary to take into account the number of movements in them, the result of their performance. In the handball game, various movements are used: walking,

running, jumping, sudden stops, turns and various jumps. The contestants will try to gain an advantage by completing the game's Sul together with their partner.

Sports games in particular handball play an important role in promoting a healthy lifestyle and strengthening the health of students. However sports being engaged in games is not enough for the organism to develop harmoniously completely. Therefore, it is better to engage in gymnastics and other sports for full development from the physical side.

Handball is one of the most common sports, it is one of the most popular and, consequently, one of the most convenient means for the physical development of schoolchildren, the development of their health. This is a truly popular game for adults, both teenagers and young people, which is equally acceptable.

Loads have a positive effect on the development of all functional systems in the body. Under the influence of training, such qualities as speed reaction, chamfering, creative thinking, speed and initiative develop, thereby improving the mental activity of participants in competitions.

The handball game can serve as a good tool for overall physical training. Handball is a series of sports games, which are considered necessary for a student of any specialty, due to the fact that he / she has acquired physical qualities, at the same time willful qualities, tactical thinking, with a variety of running, different types of jumping, maximum speed of movement and weight loss.

The handball game is widely used in educational institutions today. Handball competitions are an excellent means of attracting students to regular physical education classes, sports skills. The concentration of the increase is one of the main factors in fulfilling the normative requirements of "Alpomish and all".

Hand ball classes are a basic form of training, like other physical education classes. The activities of the participants in the lesson are headed by the reader.

This creates the most favorable conditions for carrying out the process of physical education. Exercises in the school sports Circle (Octagon) are organized in the form of a QAM lesson.

The general educational objectives of the handball lessons defined in the program are to be articulated in the system of private tasks during the planning of work for a certain period (school year, quarter training phase and khokazo). The results of the work are primarily determined by the correct structure of a lesson from didactic gist.

Students of the upper classes should be provided for the educational tasks of the course of

the training lesson. Materials for the acquisition of knowledge, skills and skills: regular understandingtirib go, the use of a variety of mesh majmu sets, physical concentration is achieved by proper manipulation of the Ruhi loads.

The educational and health-improving tasks of the handball lessons are determined by the general educational and educational work plan. This person finds the main entrances of Fe, upbringing of physical abilities, development of health, but it is possible to carry out them not only with a regular impact on the functions of his organism, but also with a concentration on the individual of the reader. These tasks are laid out before several classes, while in training in alokhi it is possible to clarify.

To organize the lesson correctly and competently from the pedagogical framework this is, first of all, the rational use of the lesson time. The most important condition for the successful conduct of the lesson is to change the working skills of students in the main and closing parts of the preparation for the lesson. It requires the teacher to properly develop the structure of the lesson. The lesson can have several independent sections. For example, the lesson can be conducted as a whole game lesson (or rather a game). In it, a number of tasks. the ball with a straight hand learning to increase concentration, getting acquainted with the technique of breaking and hitting, improving the pulse by increasing the block column, developing the qualities of speedtirishga training exercises aimed at Rev.the G.

The essence of the correct drawing up of such a lesson is to mentally correct the pedagogical and zyphs in the correct order, to achieve compliance of the participants with the possibilities of cable weight loss. In this, the phases of change in the ability of the participants to engage are taken into account in the most optimal norms.

Organization of handball classes should begin before the training: this dressing is the observance of the order in the dressing room, the sports equipment is well prepared for the lesson, the duty of the guards is to perform their duties in full, the class is to sort out in its own right before going to the training ground, so that the Home task is to

Good preparation for the lesson will determine its success, a positive mood will make it possible to make a more intense concentration of the dressing.

The handball game is now becoming one of the main tools of physical education in the system of Physical Culture. Through the periods of preparation of the gandbolists, the types of preparation, the periods of their preparation and its planning, the physical preparation and special physical preparation of the gandbolists will be achieved in the above plan. General physical training is a necessary preparation of schoolchildren in the upper class, as it is the main

ground for the education of special physical training, as well as for the physical convenience for the engaged in mastering the technique and tactics of the handball game.

1. Special physical training is one of the main preparations in the activities of schoolchildren in the upper class, it is the main factor that determines the effectiveness of the participation of the wanderer in the game.

2. Special physical training is a physical ground for performing all the movements in the game activity of the handball, trained in the upper class on the basis of general physical training of handball players.

3. All movements that are encountered in the game of the handball or are included in its composition are exercises that require special agility, special agility, special endurance, special strength elasticity, qualities are not only necessary for their activity in the game or competition, but also the main physical comfort factor in the learning process, because in the study of each movement, the handball manifests certain

4. When educating the general physical training of schoolchildren in the upper class, all physical exercises can be used as a tool.

5. Athletic exercises according to the purpose and tasks set for the implementation of special physical training of schoolchildren in the upper class will be a means of gymnastic exercises and Universal exercises.

6. In the upper class, the technical preparation of schoolchildren is from the basic preparation of the player, which is carried out during the entire preparation process, in addition to the correct selection of the methodology for teaching technical preparation for full-fledged training, it is mandatory that each player has a sufficient level of physical preparation, the correct use of the principles of the progress of all educational

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